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CONSTRUCTION OF A TEXT ASSOCIATIVE SEMANTIC FIELD AS A MEANS OF REVEALING EMOTIONAL AND EVALUATIVE OVERTONES IN LITERARY DISCOURSE (BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF V. NABOKOV'S SHORT STORY "TERROR")

Daria Zhgun

Ph.D. in Philology,

Catholic University of Daegu

13-13 Hayang-ro, Hayang-eup, Gyeongsan-si, 38430, South Korea

Abstract

The article focuses on discovering emotional and evaluative overtones in Vladimir Nabokov's short story "Terror." Based on a thorough examination of the story and meticulous analysis of dictionary and thesaurus definitions of the notions conveying emotions in it, the author constructs a text associative semantic field (TASF) with the nucleus represented by the lexeme "terror" and the periphery with its synonyms and associations. Such an approach to researching an artwork's overall emotional tone constitutes the paper's novelty. The study has demonstrated that many words belonging to the field appear to be involved in diverse linguistic devices that are dispersed throughout the story and create a more sophisticated layer of meaning and subcontext that allows for a more profound understanding of the character's emotional state and detection of hidden emotional and evaluative overtones. Specifically, apart from the leading emotion of terror and its synonyms from the fear cluster, multiple emotional and evaluative overtones have been discovered, including terror-disgust, terror-rage, terror-surprise, and terror-grief. Overall, the comprehensive linguistic investigation has proven the complexity and depth of human emotions, the unique character of their verbal representation, and the multi-layered nature of the short story where they are so skillfully concealed.

Keywords: semantic field, text associative field, emotion, emotional and evaluative overtone, literary discourse, short story, Nabokov.

*This is more than quick recoverable terror,
And we, watching the hanging waiting darkness,
Counting the moments of the coming storm,
Find it not easy now to stand erect.*

G. Allen

Being one of the leading and promising areas of linguistics in the past several decades, the systematic study of language and speech has led to the emergence of a considerable body of works dedicated to the theory of semantic fields. First put forward by German and Swiss linguists (Ipsen, Porzig, Trier), it has been further developed by Ullmann, Geckeler, Weisgerber, Pokrovsky, Admoni, Bondarko, Gak, and Shchur. Overall, the idea of the field approach lies in the belief that the vocabulary of any language is an integrated system of lexemes interrelated in the sense that "the value of a word can only be determined by defining it in relation to the value of neighbouring and contrasting words" and that the meaning exists only in the field (Trier, 1934, p. 428). Generally, a *semantic field* is defined as a lexical set of semantically related items or a hierarchical structure consisting of multiple lexical units. As a rule, a semantic field has a *nucleus* that is presented by a hyperseme that expresses the most general meaning, a *center* that is comprised of lexical units that share the meaning with the nucleus, and a *periphery* that includes lexical units that have a more distant, potential, or probable meaning in regard to the nucleus.

As a way of reflecting a particular part of reality in the human mind, a semantic field constitutes the plane of content, whereas the plane of expression can

be embodied by various subtypes of the semantic field, including phrase-semantic, functional-semantic, morpho-semantic, and lexico-semantic. Many papers are dedicated to the latter, defined as a set of particular words that belong to the same part of speech and share the meaning component. However, when the semantic structure of individual words is taken into account, it becomes evident that they belong to different lexical sets, where some are clearly defined "narrow notions," and others are unclear "broad notions" strongly impacted by personal connotations (Katz, 1972, p. 450). In other words, the underlying definition strictly determines the meaning of the words belonging to the first group. In contrast, the meaning of the words from the second group is "implicitly defined by the semantic and syntactic rules governing their use in speech acts" and varies based on individual interpretations of speech acts that include the respective word (Fonagy, 2001, p. 9). The fact that natural languages are "intrinsically incapable of precise characterization" (Zadeh, 1978, p. 4) makes some notions fuzzy, which, in turn, leads to the lexico-semantic fields these notions belong to being also fuzzy and diffused (Zhgun, 2022). Therefore, constructing solely lexico-semantic fields of notions does not always suffice to understand their whole meaning. This is especially true regarding inherently ambiguous notions that express emotions.

As a subjective reaction to the inner or outer stimuli based on individual appraisal, emotions prove to be a highly complex phenomenon of the human psyche that demands careful investigation. What makes emotions difficult to cognize is that they are perceived

somewhat differently by different people and, as a result, are diversely represented in the language. On the one hand, dictionaries provide practical definitions and typical examples of the usage of words representing emotions. On the other hand, they short-circuit the procedure of how speakers and writers perceive and apply these words in real life. Much evidence to prove that the ways people evaluate situations and react to them emotionally and verbally differ can be found in literary discourse – a complex communicative phenomenon that manifests itself in the form of a literary text created by the author to impact the reader. In turn, a literary text is a sophisticated system of images, meanings, and ideas that must be deciphered, understood, and interpreted in the process of perception (Chirkova, 2018, p. 98). Being the work of art and imagination of a particular author, a literary text also reflects his / her worldview, values, experience, spiritual seeking, and certainly emotions. It is usually easy to decode an emotion in the text even when it is not expressed but described or implied. However, it is quite another matter when the author conveys mixed emotions belonging to the same or different emotional clusters by resorting to diverse literary devices and techniques. In this regard, the reader must decode not only emotions but hidden emotional and evaluative overtones – concealed, inherent components of the semantic structure of words revealed within specific contextual determinants (Zhgun, 2023). In other words, covert emotional and evaluative overtones become determinable with considerable contextual expansion and the author's perception of the emotional state expressed and / or implied in the artwork – with constructing a text associative semantic field.

In this article, a *text associative semantic field* (TASF) is defined as a system of the author's verbal associations with a particular phenomenon that includes key and hint words as well as markers of associates that unitedly create an overall atmosphere of the literary work and that can be discovered by a scrupulous analysis of the text in which they are scattered. The procedure of the construction of the associative semantic field of the chosen text entails the selection of the words that represent frequent reactions and associations of the author with a specific phenomenon (in our case, it is the emotional state of the main characters), their systematization, generalization of the data obtained, and determination of their influence on understanding of the essence of the text and the author's worldview. Therefore, constructing a TASF can help trace how words extend their meaning and determine the author's subjective attitude towards this notion, which emphasizes the uniqueness of his style and the richness of his mental lexicon that entails general knowledge of the notion, multi-faceted associations, and the cultural background. Let us now refer to the emotion of fear overall and its linguistic representation in Vladimir Nabokov's short story "Terror" in particular.

In philosophy, different and sometimes contradictory viewpoints exist on the phenomenon of fear. In *The Nicomachean Ethics*, Aristotle (2003, p. 67) defines *fear* as an expectation of evil, stating that all peo-

ple are afraid of different evils, including disgrace, poverty, sickness, loss, and friendlessness. The most fearful thing of all, however, is death, because "it is the end, and it is assumed that for the dead there is no good or evil anymore" (ibid). Nevertheless, Aristotle underlines that what is dreadful is not the same for everyone, and although all people are concerned with the same fearful things, they have different attitudes towards them. In other words, everyone's appraisal of the objects of fear differs in the magnitude and intensity of fear they evoke and the reactions that follow it. The Stoics attribute the reason to the fact that people appraise things differently to individual judgment. In particular, in his moral letter to Paulinus *On the Shortness of Life*, Seneca (2007, pp. 158–159) writes that there will never be a shortage of reasons for anxieties, "whether born of happiness or misery." Although people are troubled by "alarms of different kinds," their most immense terror is that someday life will end (ibid). In his essay *On Fear*, Montaigne (1994, pp. 14–15) confidently asserts that "it is fear that I am most afraid of. In harshness, it surpasses all other mischances." The philosopher goes further in his speculations on fear and claims that it is "even more importunate and unbearable than death, for it seizes, freezes, and strangles the heart, drives people, unable to withstand its stabbing pains, to perform in its own service" (ibid). Interestingly enough, Montaigne classifies fear as a case of rapture or madness that drives people out of their minds and "ravishes our judgment from its proper seat" (ibid, p. 13). In other words, the Renaissance humanist sees fear in correlation with delirium and underscores its complex nature and the ability to produce different shades. A similar idea can be found in the works of an existential thinker, Kierkegaard (2005), who distinguishes between a regular fear based on comprehension (*Furcht*) and an inexplicable fear-sadness or fear-terror (*Angst*).

Fear has also been widely investigated in psychology, where it is defined as an emotion that emerges in situations of threat to one's biological or social existence and is targeted at the source of real or imaginary danger (Petrovsky & Yaroshevsky, 1990). Depending on the source of danger, the emotion can be differentiated in the following way: in real danger, a person experiences fear; in mysterious danger – horror; and in the combination of both – dread. Terror is felt when diverse dangerous causes are present simultaneously (Osipov, 1923). The latter is of the highest intensity, which leads to the widening of the eyes, a feeling of breathlessness, voicelessness, muscle shivering, a change in a heartbeat, unstable attention, a motionless body, "frozen thoughts," and inhibition or complete stop of the functioning of associative processes (ibid, p. 66).

Based on the cause, fear can also be classified into four major groups: 1) fear associated with a specific cause, condition, or situation; 2) fear associated with no particular reason, also known as *diffuse fear*; 3) fear of a mystical force that surpasses human imagination, or fear of God; and 4) existential fear, or fear of death (Gudkov, 1999). The latter is often accompanied by a wide range of symptoms, including panic attacks and depersonalization / derealization disorder, which refers to dissociation and a sense of alienation concerning

one’s self and environment (Gatus et al., 2022). The experience is often compared to the feeling of “being in a bubble or separated from the world by an invisible barrier such as a pane of glass, a fog, or a veil” and a sense of detachment and estrangement from one’s thinking, body, and world (Sierra & David, 2011, p. 99). Seemingly, terror is mainly a psychological phenomenon that exploits the human mind, turns one against himself, and implants disturbing thoughts of its horrifying implications. In response to such unbearable pressure of the emotion, the human mind begins to apply specific defense mechanisms to prevent the overload, including *displacement* (changing or displacing the original target of the impulse to another target), *repression* (unconsciously repressing feelings, memories or thoughts from the consciousness), *suppression* (the conscious effort to avoid certain feelings and thoughts), and *rationalization* (creating excuses and explanations to events or actions in rational terms) (Baumeister et al., 1998).

As a primary universal emotion, fear with all its shades and symptoms finds multiple manifestations at all levels of language, including interjections (*Oh my God! Holy Cow! Jeez! What the hell! Yikes!*), direct nomination (*fear, anxiety, trepidation, fright, scare, twinge, alarm*), description (*his heart leaped into his*

throat, she trembled inside, his legs became wobbly, his stomach clenched), tropes and figures of speech (*fear spiked, terror sealed her throat, fear made my blood run cold, it struck terror in my heart, they were on pins and needles, I was quaking in my boots*). The semantic primitives for fear entail “bad, do, happen, know” (Wierzbicka, 1972, pp. 59–63). To put it another way, the semantic field of the notion of fear comprises a variety of forms expressing the belief that something terrible is about to happen shortly. Therefore, it is unsurprising that it is so broad. The reference to several dictionaries (Merriam-Webster, Cambridge, Collins, Oxford) and thesauri (Roget’s Thesaurus, Visual Thesaurus, English Dictionary of Emotional Phrases) allows for determining the semantic field of the notion with a nucleus *fear*, the center that contains its close synonyms (*dread, alarm, apprehension, phobia, creeps, pang, agitation, intimidation, nervousness, trepidation, startle, scare, concern, anxiety, spook, fright, worry, panic, horror, being afraid, chill, and terror*), and the periphery that includes near-synonyms and associates (*calamity, agony, torment, misery, distress, unease, astonishment, cravenness, cowardice, perturbation, hesitation, timidity, shock, doubt, dismay, calamity*). Visually, it is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Lexico-semantic field of the notion “fear”

The figure demonstrates that fear can be expressed by multiple synonyms, thus possessing different degrees of intensity. The list of synonyms presented can be further extended based on the study of more resources.

The analysis of dictionary definitions of the notions from the fear cluster also allows for the construction of a gradual cluster, where the notion of fear is taken as a starting point due to being the most neutral and having the most considerable number of properties

and similarities with other group members and is defined as an unpleasant often strong emotion caused by anticipation or awareness of danger; anxious concern (Zhgun, 2022). Unlike fear, *dread* is defined as great fear, especially in the face of impending evil; extreme uneasiness; *horror* – as painful fear or dread; intense aversion or repugnance; and *terror* – a state of intense fear; sharp, overmastering fear. The gradual cluster is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Gradual cluster of the emotion “fear”

The figure shows that terror is the most intense emotion from the fear cluster. More of its definitions are provided below:

- a state of **intense** or **overwhelming** fear (Merriam-Webster Dictionary),
- **extreme** fear in the presence of **danger** or **evil** (Collins Dictionary),
- more violent than feeling spooked, more immediate than dread, less connected to gore and disgust than horror, an emotion that is felt in the presence of an **elusive, unseen menace** and leaves one rigid, rooted to the spot (Smith, 2015, p. 259).

As seen from the definitions, terror implies the feeling of alienation and extreme invisible and inexplicable suspense that the emotion evokes. Also, it is often felt in sudden, uncontrollable situations of danger. Such fierce nature of terror is also supported by the Word Associations Network (URL), where the word *terror* includes the following associations: 1) nouns: shriek, agony, dismay, remorse, scourge, repression, trembling, purge, despair, nightmare, suspense, shudder, bloodshed, brutality, torture, atrocity, 2) adjectives: stricken, paralyzed, superstitious, sheer, ghastly, stark, speechless, frantic, hideous, quivering, awful, mortal, inexplicable, haunting, helpless, utter, creeping, crouching, 3) verbs: to scream, to unleash, to shrink, to flee, to tremble, to utter, to mingle, to faint, to menace, to beset, to overwhelm, to inflict, to shudder, and 4) adverbs: madly, wildly, ghostly.

Fear overall, and terror in particular, has often been the focus of attention and speculation by many authors. As a result, a broad scope of examples of linguistic representation of fear and its synonyms can be found in literature:

(1) *She was so **afraid** of seeing him that her **stomach was in knots** and she thought she was going to be sick* (Kundera, 2000, p. 146).

(2) *Lenina suddenly felt all the sensations normally experienced at the beginning of a Violent Passion Surrogate treatment – a sense of **dreadful** emptiness, a **breathless apprehension**, a nausea. Her **heart seemed to stop beating*** (Huxley, 200, p. 174).

(3) *He had been standing by the lift for three hours. He was **on his fifth cigarette**, and his **mind was skittering*** (Barnes, 2016, p. 3).

(4) *It was a rhythmic, quick, blunt sound, and Cincinnatus, **all his nerves a-flutter**, heard in it an invitation* (Nabokov, 2001, p. 54).

(5) *One of the watchers forgot himself, began to applaud, and suddenly backed away, **eyes cloudy with terror*** (King, 2017, p. 49).

The specifics of the emotional state have been particularly skillfully conveyed in Vladimir Nabokov’s short story “Terror” (Nabokov, 2008). Published in 1927, the story is a quick read about death, life, relationships, and one’s place in the world. It follows the narrative of a very self-reflexive poet who undergoes several panic attacks and a pathological feeling of de-personalization, when he does not recognize himself in the mirror (*[...] the harder I found it to make the face in the mirror merge with that “I” whose identity I failed to grasp; I had grown disacquainted with myself; I now stood considering my own reflection in the glass and failing to recognize it as mine; that fleeting sensation of estrangedness; those unblinking alien eyes*) and derealization, when he does not register his girl’s identity (*[...] somehow, for a split second, my mind did not register her identity in the dusty sun of the station; I am terrified by there being another person in the room with me*) and does not recognize the world around him, but perceives it as it is, unfiltered through habitual categorization, with its nakedness and meaninglessness (*I saw the actual essence of all things; [...] and that world was devoid of sense*), which is caused by his exhaustion and lack of sleep (*I would get up from my chair feeling chilly and utterly spent; I slept badly for three nights in a row; I had a lot of things to take care of, and I smoked a lot; Insomnia had left me with an exceptionally receptive void within my mind; Well – on that terrible day when, devastated by a sleepless night*). All of this induces a sense of supreme terror of death and a feeling of insanity (*I would abruptly remember that I was mortal; the sudden pang of death’s foretaste; the helpless fear of existing*), which the poet tries to displace by putting out the light, deliberately whistling or humming, bringing back his childhood memories, maintaining rigid self-control, and even finding temporary salvation in grief.

With his inherent imaginative mastery, Nabokov details the emotional state and thoughts of the main

character and creates a credible atmosphere of horrifying pangs of fear he experiences. Being a brilliant virtuoso of language, the author uses diverse literary devices and figures of speech to convey the existential fear that grips the main character with the severity of a heart attack. Together, they facilitate the unity of the story. Let us provide some examples.

The first group includes excerpts that convey different overtones of the emotion of fear through direct nomination:

(6) *In point of fact, once or twice, late at night, I peered so lengthily at my reflection that a **creepy** feeling came over me and I put out the light in a hurry* (p. 173).

(7) [...] *in the dark, from the cheapest seats, in one's private theater where warm live thoughts about dear earthly trifles have **panicked**, there comes a shriek* [...] (p. 174).

(8) *All at once, for no reason at all, I become **terrified** of her presence. This is far more **terrifying** than the fact that somehow, for a split second, my mind did not register her identity in the dusty sun of the station* (p. 174).

(9) *I laughed and began talking to her, but then felt that she had clutched my wrist and was silently **worrying** my wrist* (p. 175).

(10) *She shook her head, chiding herself with a deprecatory smile for her childish **fright** – but then burst into tears and asked to be taken home* (p. 175).

(11) *When getting ready for bed in my hotel room, I would deliberately whistle or hum but would start like a **fearful** child at the slightest noise behind me, such as the flop of my jacket slipping from the chairback to the floor* (p. 176).

(12) *I understood the **horror** of a human face* (p. 177).

(13) *Just as a man who is having a heart attack on a sidewalk does not give a hoot for the passerby, the sun, the beauty of an ancient cathedral, and has only one **concern**: to breathe, so I too had only one desire: not to go mad* (p. 177).

Apart from nomination, Nabokov pays close attention to the intensity of the poet's emotions, their depth, strength, unrestraint, and novelty (*supreme (special, odd) terror, acute unrelieved anguish, helpless fear of existing*). In addition, there is an abundance of metaphoric inventiveness as well as many illustrations of personifications of the narrator's emotional state:

(14) ***Overwhelmed with terror**, I sought support in some basic idea, some better brick than the Cartesian one, with the help of which to begin the reconstruction of the simple, natural, habitual world* (p. 177).

(15) *It was in the foreign city I reached next day that I was to have my **encounter with supreme terror*** (p. 176).

(16) *In this darkness everything at once began to move, a **shiver of panic** began to rise and resolved itself in feminine cries* [...] (p. 175).

(17) [...] *with the **black thunder of panic** growing – until suddenly the lights come on again, and the performance of the play is blandly resumed* (p. 174).

The last example is of particular interest. The emotion of fear is expressed by its synonym – panic. The

notion is located a few steps higher on the gradual cluster due to its higher intensity:

- a **sudden uncontrollable** fear or anxiety, often causing **wildly unthinking** behavior (Oxford English Dictionary),

- a sudden overwhelming fear, with or without cause, that produces **hysterical** or **irrational** behavior, and that often **spreads quickly** through a group of persons (Collins Dictionary).

The emotional state is conveyed metaphorically – *the black thunder of panic* – where *thunder* is defined as the **sudden** loud noise that comes from the sky during the storm (Cambridge Dictionary). The definitions show that the emotional state is associated with a natural phenomenon based on its unexpectedness and uncontrollability. In addition, the adjective *dark* emphasizes the negative impacts of panic as it causes one to lose rationality and clear thinking.

A broad palette of compositional techniques to convey the emotional state of terror is also applied in the short story, including inversion and repetition:

(18) *In vain **did I try** to master my terror* (p. 177).

(19) *While I traveled back, while I sat at her bedside, it never occurred to me to analyze the meaning of being and nonbeing, and no longer **was I terrified** by those thoughts* (p. 178).

(20) ***I am terrified** by there being another person in the room with me; **I am terrified** by the very notion of another person* (p. 174).

The author also resorts to the convergence method or the simultaneous usage of two or more linguistic devices. Let us analyze one particular example that perfectly delivers the main character's emotional state.

(21) *Thus would my soul **choke** for a moment while, **lying supine, eyes wide open**, I tried with **all my might to conquer fear**, rationalize death, come to terms with it on a day-by-day basis, without appealing to any creed or philosophy* (p. 174).

In this case, the emotional state of already ingrowing fear is linguistically represented by several means, including direct nomination (*fear*) and description (*lying supine, eyes wide open*), which shows the negative influence of fear on the poet, i.e., its ability to stop him from falling asleep. Also, the uncontrollable nature of fear is conveyed by the metaphor *to conquer* and the phrase *with all my might*. Fear is also implied in the phrase *Thus would my soul choke*, where the verb *to choke* is used metaphorically, implying that fear stops the main character from breathing by strangling him. In other words, the analysis of the excerpt demonstrates that convergence allows for more expressivity, creating a more vivid image of the emotion of fear.

Quite often, the emotional state of fear and its synonyms is solely implied in the story:

(22) *I saw that she was **pale** and that her **teeth were clenched**. I helped her to get out of the lodge* (p. 175).

(23) [...] *even though you realize that **the frost of this mysterious anesthesia** will presently wear off* (p. 173).

Both examples show the paralyzing effects of extreme fear: in example (22), it makes the woman mo-

tionless by preventing her from getting out of the theater by herself, whereas in example (23), it is conveyed by metaphors of *frost* and *anesthesia* that imply the condition of feeling frozen and numb accordingly.

Being quite obsessed with reaching for the most precise word for the emotional state, the author, however, is sometimes incapable of (or deliberately trying to avoid) verbalizing the character's feelings in order to create a more true-to-life atmosphere:

(24) *Supreme terror, special terror – I am groping for the exact term but my store of ready-made words, which in vain I keep trying on, does not contain even the one that will fit* (p. 174).

(25) *Once only – and here again I feel what a clumsy instrument human speech is* (p. 174).

Notably, the excerpts show the narrator's failed attempt to find suitable words to express his terror. The unique character of the emotion that is unnamed and has never been experienced either by him or others is implied in the metaphor *my store of ready-made words* which conveys the absence of suitable words. In addition, the verb *to grope* (to feel about **blindly** or **uncertainty** in search) adds more to the description of the narrator's despair to verbalize his emotional experience. The condition is known as *alexithymia*, or the inability or difficulty to express emotions verbally, an emotional overwhelm. Frequently, authors resort to the linguistic representation of alexithymia when they want to underline the intensity of the emotion, create a pragmatic effect, or leave space for the reader's imagination (Zhgun, 2020). The latter is significant because "it is our imagination and our sympathy which communicates our emotion" and "the resource of conveying our emotion to each other does not depend upon the wealth of words only" (Markino, 1913, p. 480). Indeed, the idea does not imply a complete ignorance or disparagement of the beauty of rhetoric and words, especially in literature.

Apart from diverse linguistic devices used to express and imply the emotional state of terror of the main character, the story has many hidden ideas that expose more importance and detail through closer reading and rereading that Nabokov himself insisted on so often. More specifically, there is a clear parallel between associating the narrator's overall state with darkness on the one hand and the lightness of a happy being on the other, or his perplexity of the mind on the one hand and clarity and transparency of thinking that can come to his rescue on the other. Linguistically, such parallels are expressed by several associates of the author and are scattered throughout the whole story that can be revealed with the investigation of the general context. To illustrate, it is evident from the analysis of the short story that the poet's bouts of extreme fear mainly occur at night or in dark places. Thus, the emotion is implied in terms of opaqueness and is conveyed by associates such as *night*, *shade*, *in the dark*, *in the darkness*, *in the darkish vestibule*, *blind*, or *black*. Contrarily, the purity and emotional maturity of the poet's girlfriend that he admired and subconsciously strived for (*It was exactly that gentle simplicity of hers that protected me: to her, everything in the world had a kind of everyday clarity, and it would even seem to me that she knew what*

awaited us after death, so that there was no reason for us to discuss the topic) is implied in the idea of lightness and transparency (*glow with warmth, the lights, tawny sunlight, a strand of fair hair, gleam touchingly, pale-gold decorations, bright eyes, inflamed little eye of the sun, sunlight flooded her room, a kind of everyday clarity, the looking glass, a mirror, glazed vault, one ear, translucently pink*). It is essential to note that the dichotomy of dark and light permeates many of Nabokov's works, where death and the unknown is associated with darkness (*And common sense tells us that our existence is but a brief crack of light between two eternities of darkness*). In contrast, the victory of mind and reflexive consciousness over the fear of death and time pressure is associated with light (*Judging by the strong sunlight that, when I think of that revelation, immediately invades my memory with lobed sun flecks through overlapping patterns of greenery*) (Nabokov, 2000, p. 5). In that respect, Bitsilli (1970, p. 117) believes that many of Nabokov's works are characterized by "a revival of allegorical art." Regarding the images of darkness and lightness, one can notice the reference to Gnosis, which is based on a belief in the dualism of divine (light, pneumatic) and demiurgical (dark, hylic) (Ginza, p. 14, as cited in Davydov, 1982). Created by the Demiurge, man's soul is trapped in his body and has to live in constant fear of death in the "dead house" in the state of "an unconscious dormant monad" (Davydov, 1982, p. 110). However, there is a possibility of salvation, but only to "the chosen" ones, who have a divine spark in them or who "are enlightened in their spiritual part by a ray from the divine light" (ibid, p. 123). In other words, the gnostic dualism of dark and light is fulfilled in the oppositions expressed and implied in the short story, where the poet is constantly living in fear and in the dark of the unknown that imbues his existence (*I would emerge from the trance of my task at the exact moment when the night had reached the summit and was teetering on the crest*;), unlike his girlfriend who exists in the light and transparency and is permeated with such light substance (e.g. *one ear, translucently pink, is half concealed by a strand of fair hair*). In addition, the antagonistic nature of the poet's darkness and the girl's lightness is implied in his recollections and a dream about her. The latter he, in fact, found "so unpleasant, so hideous" (*but good God! How I loved her unassuming prettiness, gaiety, friendliness, the birdlike flutterings of her soul; The first night I saw my girl in dream: sunlight flooded her room, and she sat on the bed wearing only a lacy nightgown, and laughed, and laughed, could not stop laughing*).

Apart from the allegoric motifs, the story contains a few meaningful symbols. To illustrate, when describing the girl's appearance, Nabokov resorts to his beloved symbol of a butterfly (*[...] from which I helped her to extricate her slender silk-clad legs – and I thought of those delicate moths that hatch from bulky shaggy cocoons*) and a pearl (*[...] and the small pearls around her neck gleam touchingly; With her bare elbow she almost knocked down from the plush parapet her little nacreous opera glasses*). In the dictionary of symbols, a butterfly with its life cycle is an emblem of

immortality that provides an analogy of life (the crawling caterpillar), death (the chrysalis) and rebirth or resurrection (the butterfly fluttering free); it also represents soul and transient joy as well as the ability to adjust to life and strive for the beauty (Tresidder, 2005, p. 80). In turn, a pearl is considered an allegoric symbol of heaven and pure soul, spiritual maturity, innocence, femininity, and light (ibid, p. 376). In other words, both symbols are applied to the girl and imply her lightness and innocence. Another predominantly positive symbol is the mirror, which typically means enlightenment, self-knowledge, sincerity, and purity (Tresidder, 2005, p. 318). Yet, the poet cannot recognize himself in the mirror and “merge” his face with his identity, so he rushes to get away from it and switch off the light. Since the mirror never lies, it is possible to assume that the poet is afraid of the truth and denies his true nature. In this regard, he refers to the idea of doppelgangers (*[...] so that there were two of me standing before her: I myself, whom she did not see, and my double, who was invisible to me*), which also implies a split in his personality and his separateness from the world. The latter he acutely experiences during his pangs of terror (*My line of communication with the world snapped, I was on my own and the world was on its own*). The inability to recognize himself in the mirror might also imply his failure to adequately reflect the whole reality, which often symbolizes “moral blindness” and “creative impotence” (Krashennikov, 2014, p. 86). Indeed, under a careful investigation of the story, it becomes clear that the poet is going through an artistic crisis – he cannot sleep well, exhausts himself with work effortlessly looking for inspiration, feels “utterly spent,” and often cannot find the right words to express himself. As a result, he feels emotional burnout and constant anxiety.

All this underlines the poet’s incapacity to fight his inner darkness.

The study of the allegorical motifs and symbols adds more to the understanding of the poet’s state and demonstrates that the story is much more than a simple description of his existential fear of death or insanity. It is sort of Nabokov’s way of exposing the poet’s mediocrity and belonging to the mundane world of things rather than to the heavenly world of imagination. Also, the short story exemplifies a double victory of darkness over light. The first victory is implied in the death of a pure and light girl, as opposed to the unbearable life of a paranoid and dark poet. The second victory is more of an existential character and implies the triumph of the poet’s fears over his soul, which can be confirmed in the concluding lines of the story.

The abovementioned analysis of linguistic means conveying the emotional state of terror together with a thorough inspection of the author’s symbolic associations through communicative signals present in the short story allows for constructing the text associative semantic field of the notion of terror represented in the short story. The nucleus is verbalized by the lexeme *terror* and its derivatives (*terrifying, terrified, terrible*), the center includes its synonyms (*fear / fearful, horror, a creepy feeling, panic / to panic, concern, to worry, fright / frightening*), and the periphery contains author’s associates with the emotion (*unpleasant / hideous / nauseated, madhouse / lunatics / to go mad / delirium / insanity, dark / darkish / darkness / in the dark / shade / black / night, mortal / death, odd / alien / estrangedness, mysterious, absurd / absurdity, chilly / frost, anesthesia, aimless, tortured, doomed, to scream / cries / a shriek / shrilly, tempest, astonishment, anguish / pain, odd / alien / estrangedness, unpleasant / hideous / nauseated, doomed, absurd / absurdity, mysterious, tortured*). Visually, the field is presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Text associative semantic field of the notion “terror”

As seen from Figure 3, the periphery constitutes the most voluminous part of the field. The most frequently associated with the emotion of terror are madness, darkness, death, and screams that convey different ways of causation and representation of the emotion. The text associative semantic field reflects the author's unique worldview and idiosyncrasy that helps reveal more shades of the emotion under study as well as new emotional and evaluative overtones, including panic terror, terror-disgust, terror-rage, terror-surprise, and terror-grief, which emerge in the result of the analysis of the relation between the nucleus and close and distant peripheries of the field. In turn, the context analysis adds more clarity to the interpretation of the overtones. For instance, being fed up with pangs of terror, the poet also feels disgusted at his incapacity to overcome it (terror-disgust) and enraged at the absurdity of the causes of his terror (terror-rage). In addition, the perplexity before the mirror and the morning astonishment at the terror of questioning reality imply that the character often experiences two emotions simultaneously (terror-surprise). Finally, together with feeling consciously or subconsciously terrified of the recurrence of fear attacks, the poet feels extreme grief after losing his girl (terror-grief).

Thus, the construction of the text associative semantic field of the notion of terror in Nabokov's eponymous short story has shown that it can actualize the senses that are not reflected in dictionaries and thesauri but present in the author's consciousness and help reveal the implied emotional and evaluative overtones of the emotion. In addition, a detailed linguistic analysis has provided conclusive evidence that there exists a rich repertoire of means conveying a refined collection of fears verbally that demonstrates a high degree of the individualization of the writer's world perception. The perspectives of the research might include the study of other genres of literary discourse. Also, in analyzing Nabokov as a bilingual author, there is a promising field of comparing and contrasting the content of the text associative semantic fields based on the analysis of his artwork both in Russian and English.

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